

Building tomorrow today: an artist's journey from European dreams to democratic reality

Interview / Photographic documentation

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Abstract

This interview explores questions of migration, citizenship, and creative resistance in contemporary Europe through a conversation with Marta Romankiv, a Ukrainian artist and activist based in Poland. Romankiv reflects on her experience of Ukraine's Revolution of Dignity in 2013–14, her migration to Poland, and the path that led her to advocacy. The discussion examines how arts-based activism and solidarity point toward a Europe of care and openness, in resistance to the exclusion, exploitation and democratic rollback sweeping across the continent. It highlights Romankiv's role in establishing a trade union for Ukrainian care workers in Poland, and fellow artists' contributions in supporting their cause through theatre, music, video, design and visual performance. Drawing on her dual perspective as both migrant and artist, Romankiv reflects on the precarity shared across creative and care professions, the challenges of political engagement for non-citizens, and art's capacity to expand collective imaginaries of what is possible. The piece includes documentation of the March for Care Workers held in Warsaw in April 2025, where domestic workers performed original protest songs demanding dignity and rights.

Keywords

migration, care work, domestic workers, Ukraine, Poland, creative activism, migrant rights, European democracy, trade unions, political art

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Building tomorrow today: an artist's journey from European dreams to democratic reality

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At a time when democratic values face unprecedented assault – from the rising tide of supremacist ideologies to brutal violations of international law and human rights – the words of Toni Cade Bambara resonate with renewed urgency: “The role of the artist is to make revolution irresistible.” At this critical juncture, artists and activists stand as essential defenders of our collective future. This conversation between Mathilde Gingembre and Marta Romankiv, a Ukrainian artist and activist based in Poland, reveals how creative resistance can transform into democratic action. Through her work organising migrant care workers, creating politically engaged art and advocating for migrants’ rights, Marta demonstrates how democracy survives not just in institutions, but through persistent engagement and the courage to imagine better futures, even in the darkest times.

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→ What if you, Mr. President, needed a nanny?
 What would you want her to do?
 How would you like her to live? [...]
 Would she have enough money to buy winter boots?
 Winter jacket, winter trip to the dentist, winter dreams?
 And what if she was not from Ukraine, but from Nigeria?
 Do these things affect you?
 Does it change anything for you?
 Mr. President, what will you do to make our care work better?
 In this eternal river of need
 In times of war and inflation
 In these days and during the holidays?
 We want our full lives¹

These hip-hop lyrics, performed by Ukrainian domestic workers in the heart of Warsaw, cut to the core of an everyday injustice – doing essential work that holds societies together while remaining invisible and denied basic dignity. This was the March for Care Workers, co-organised by Ukrainian artist-activist Marta Romankiv and the Association of Theatre Pedagogues in April 2025. It was creative activism at its best: using art to foreground migrants' critical economic contributions while demanding their rights to respect, protection, and dignity. At a time when growing numbers of people fleeing political violence encounter Europe's fortress-like borders, their struggle for collective futures built on solidarity rather than exclusion needs to be heard.

I first met Marta at the "EU Meets Europe" project launch in Genshagen (Germany), where we connected over our shared experience as researchers living in Poland and common interest in forced displacement and the rights of migrants. Through this process, I discovered Marta's quiet engagement supporting Ukrainian domestic workers and winning concrete victories for their rights here in Poland. As a European outraged by the deadly cost of restrictive migration policies – and a nomadic, working mother who relies on care work – this story resonated deeply. When Marta invited me to the March for Care Workers, I witnessed a protest unlike any I'd seen – choreographed performances where women draped in orange capes carried golden megaphones, handcrafted for the march, broadcasting the voices of care workers who were too frightened or unable to be there themselves, integrated with costumes and protest songs. This was the European story I'd been searching for – one of solidarity, creativity, and the fight for a more just Europe. I brought my sons to the demonstration, creating a formative moment in their understanding of migrants' struggles and the power of collective action. And as I heard them chanting the lyrics of the protest songs on the bus back home, Toni Cade Bambara's words echoed in my mind: 'The role of the artist is to make revolution irresistible'.

The following interview explores Marta's journey from childhood dreams of Europe to her current work supporting marginalised migrant women, demonstrating how everyday acts of creative resistance and solidarity offer vital hope for Europe's democratic future.

Mathilde Gingembre (MG): Could you tell me about your earliest memories and perceptions of Europe and the European Union as a child growing up in Ukraine?

Marta Romankiv (MR): The word "Europe" always meant something far away, something you had to cross the border to reach. It always represented something better. I remember my father going to Poland on trucks; he used to bring sweets and juices that we didn't have in Ukraine in the late 1990s. On one occasion, he managed to bring home frozen chickens, which we later stuffed into our freezer. Trips to the western border – to Europe – were associated with prosperity for me as a child.

MG: So Europe was associated with material abundance. Was there also a political dimension to these perceptions?

MR: Yes, absolutely. Even the word "European" – like European clothes, European food – we still have it a lot in Ukraine in the public sphere, and it always means some additional value, that it's better because it's European. But there was also this interesting dissonance –

¹ Members of the Domestic Workers' Commission, "*Panie Prezydencie*" (Mr. President), music and vocals by Magdalena Sowul. Compiled and edited by Dorota Ogrodzka. Original song in Polish (free translation by Mathilde Gingembre).

In school, I heard all the time that Ukraine is in the centre of Europe, that the geographical centre of Europe is in Ukraine. Yet Europe still meant something that wasn't there.

MG: How did these early perceptions influence your decision to move to Poland for your studies?

MR: I moved to Poland in 2015 because I believed that there were better studies in art there, and also because the degree you get can be accepted in other EU countries. With a Ukrainian degree, you struggle much more to prove its validity. It's funny how you change, though – when I was 16 or 17, I couldn't imagine moving from Ukraine. I was so pro-Ukrainian that I thought I'd never leave my home country.

MG: Your journey from these childhood dreams to political activism wasn't straightforward. Could you tell us about your experience during the Revolution of Dignity in Ukraine in 2013/14?

MR: During the revolution, I remember that feeling of unity and common purpose, which was great. On the other hand, we didn't know if the revolution would succeed or not, if the police would be on our side or the other side. I remember how afraid I was to come home from the demonstrations alone. It was total chaos. There were activists disappearing from the streets and

buildings on fire. Fortunately, civil society then won against the Russian dictatorship, but after this experience, and after more than 100 deaths in Kyiv, as well as the start of the war in Ukraine in 2014, as a young person I became more cautious about participating in protests in the years that followed.

MG: How did this affect your political engagement when you moved to Poland?

MR: For the first years in Poland, I didn't engage in any movements. Even in 2016, during the Black Feminist revolution and Black protests, I didn't take part because I was afraid. As a migrant, I was worried about my papers and my future. I knew that I couldn't be detained by the police because it could affect future decisions about my stay in Poland.

MG: Could you talk about your experience adapting to life in Poland? How did your identity evolve?

MR: From the beginning, I felt great pressure to speak Polish very well, without an accent. In shops or bakeries, I didn't want people to know I was from Ukraine because they would see you differently. I had a huge complex about my Ukrainian identity. I wanted to be as Polish as possible, as fast as possible. It was different when I went to Portugal for Erasmus. In Portugal, I was just a foreigner – I could be from Poland or Ukraine, it was so far away that there weren't so many stereotypes about Ukrainians. When I came back from Portugal to Poland, I suddenly understood how people see me and how they talk with me

sometimes. It made me more aware. I saw my own emigrant experience from a different perspective, and understood that I shouldn't hide my identity, but conversely be proud of who I am. This gave me the strength to deal with the topic of migration in my artistic work.

MG: Could you tell me about how you moved from being a student in arts to organising migrant care workers? It seems like quite a journey.

MR: During my residency at the Museum of Contemporary Art in Warsaw in 2021, I found a report about Ukrainian care workers in the context of Covid. Moving into people's homes to take care of children or the elderly is quite a common way for Ukrainian women to make a living in exile. These stories resonated deeply with me, perhaps because my grandmother has been a care worker in Italy since the early 2000s. When I started looking for these workers, I discovered there was no space for them to meet, no organisation supporting them specifically. They existed in isolation, mainly connected through Facebook groups.

MG: What challenges did you face in organising these women?

MR: Many of them worked without contracts, and some didn't have legal status, so they were super afraid. Most didn't speak Polish well and spent all their time in their employers' homes. Even when they had time off, they would just walk around shopping centres because they didn't know where else to go. The only place they could meet was the Orthodox church. But when I posted about

creating a meeting space, there were hundreds of comments saying how much they wanted this. They needed a place to meet people from their country, to just talk.

MG: Both migrants and those working to support them face significant challenges in Europe today. How has the political climate affected your work?

MR: My own experience has made me realise that it's hard to stand up for your rights when you don't feel part of a society. When the far right was in government in Poland (2015-2023), there were lots of demonstrations. Since I was starting to feel integrated in Poland, I was less scared to take part than I would have been when I'd just arrived. Although, as a migrant, you always need to remain cautious. This is also how I started thinking about these issues and decided to write my Master's dissertation on migrants' rights in the context of the presidential elections in 2020. It's difficult for migrants to speak up, especially more marginalised ones. It's telling that most of the care workers who now lead our union already have good working conditions. They're fighting for others and future generations. Because many others aren't able to be outspoken in the same way – they work without contracts or have uncertain legal status, so they feel at risk. This is why we had to be creative with our protest methods, like when we used those golden megaphones to broadcast the testimonies of those care workers who don't want to show their faces.

MG: You've experienced these challenges from multiple perspectives – as a migrant, an artist and a researcher. How do these intersect?

MR: We're talking about the precarious conditions of domestic workers, but artists also face similar problems. We often work without contracts and for very low salaries. It's a different kind of precarity, but there are parallels.

MG: This reminds me of the challenges in academia, too, where there's such a shortage of public funding nowadays that a lot of us write and publish for free, just in the hope of finally landing a secure position one day...

MR: Yes, exactly, and it's very difficult when people are spread out geographically, when they're vulnerable and have to put all their energy into trying to find a job. You have no energy left for organising and getting politically engaged.

MG: Yet, despite these challenges, you've managed to create significant change. How did the care workers' union evolve from what seemed impossible to become reality?

MR: It started very simply – with tea and cakes. I put myself in the role of caring for them because they're caring for other people all the time. They shared dramatic stories about their working conditions. The idea of a trade union seemed utopian at first. But step by step, by bringing in activists and organisers to speak with them, the women began to see possibilities they hadn't imagined before.

MG: How has your understanding of Europe and democracy evolved through these experiences?

MR: The Europe I dreamed of as a child was this distant, perfect place. Then, as a migrant in Poland, I became more aware of all its democratic and inclusion failures. With time, I gained confidence and started feeling less scared to stand up for my rights, even if I come from a non-EU country. I feel stronger and more at home now. Even if, as a migrant, you always have some kind of fear of speaking up.

MG: What role do you think art plays in this process of democratic construction and personal empowerment?

MR: Art creates spaces where we can imagine different futures. Everything visible is political, as Rancière says. When we organised the demonstration, asking "where is the monument to the housemaid?" near the Adam Mickiewicz monument in Kraków, we were raising awareness of the invisible labour that has always supported society. Through art, we can put new ideas into the discourse in ways that might be more controversial or challenging than traditional political speech. When I started the project with care workers, creating a trade union seemed completely utopian. Art helps us expand what we think is possible. This is how art and activism work together – by making us see what we've overlooked and imagine what could be different. That's where I see the power of art – in creating brave visions of change.

MG: Looking to the future, what's your vision for Europe?

MR: I believe we need to imagine a Europe where migrants are more welcome and have more political rights, including voting rights for “third-country citizens” as well. I dream of a Europe where political rights aren’t tied to citizenship, where care work is valued, where art continues to push the boundaries of what we think is possible

MG: Thank you, Marta. Any final thoughts on the relationship between art, democracy and utopia?

MR: I think, from my experience, the most important thing is not to be afraid of utopian thinking. When I started organising meetings for care workers, a trade union seemed impossible. Now it exists. When I felt afraid to speak up as a migrant, political art seemed dangerous. Now it’s my tool for change. Sometimes we need to dream impossible things to make them possible.

In these turbulent times, where democratic institutions face erosion from within and violent challenges from without, stories like Marta’s illuminate paths forward. Through her work as both artist and activist, she demonstrates that democracy is not merely a political system to be defended, but a daily practice that must be actively reimagined and rebuilt. Her advocacy for migrant workers exemplifies how art can expand our conception of what is possible, while her activism transforms these expanded horizons into concrete change. As Europe and the world grapple with the rise of authoritarian movements, wars of aggression and the undermining of democratic values, Marta’s journey reminds us that resistance and hope are intertwined. In the space between dream and reality, between art and activism, between memory and hope, new forms of democratic participation emerge – not just through institutional reforms, but through the tireless work of citizens who dare to imagine and fight for better possibilities. These are the spaces where Europe’s utopias become real, one small victory at a time.

Photos by Alicja Szulc

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Photo by Marta Romankiv

